

A harmonized monitoring theoretical framework for pollination restoration Living Labs in Europe

Authors

Basaran Zehra^{1,2}, Prosperi Paolo^{1,2}, Kleftodimos Georgios^{1,2}

¹ CIHEAM-IAMM, UMR MoISA, Montpellier F-34093, France

² MoISA, Univ Montpellier, CIHEAM-IAMM, CIRAD, INRAE, Institut Agro, IRD, Montpellier, France

Abstract

Pollination is the mother core of nature. Pollinators are so referred because they are responsible for the reproduction of 75% of agricultural crops and 90% of all plants and are also estimated to contribute approximately \$127-152 billion to global economic welfare. However, wild pollinators are in danger of decline due to various conditions. Therefore, there is a need for pollination restoration. This research focuses on developing a theoretical framework for envisioning and structuring new policies for pollination restoration in living labs, transdisciplinary environments based on stakeholder engagement. A transdisciplinary monitoring theoretical framework is developed combining the social-ecological systems framework approach, principles of innovation economy, and the participatory social learning approach within the scope of 16 Living Labs in Europe within the Horizon Europe project RestPoll.

Key words

Living Labs, Innovation, Socio-Ecological Systems, Pollinator Restoration, Monitoring Theoretical Framework

Context

In Europe, pollination plays a crucial role in European ecology and agriculture from east to west, north to south (Lanssens et al., 2022; Persson et al., 2023; Bottero et al., 2023). Therefore, studies have been carried out on this topic for many years. For example, pollinator studies in Europe have documented several declines in wild bee populations over the years, which has led to increased interest in pollination restoration (Arbetman et al. 2017; Biesmeijer et al. 2006; Cameron et al. 2011; Goulson et al. 2008; Nooten et al. 2020; Potts et al. 2010; van Dooren 2019). One of the reasons why pollinators are so important in Europe and why so much research is being done on them is that there are around two thousand species of bees in this region, but only 34% of them are considered to be of at least some concern, while data on more than half are not validated (Nieto et al. 2014). In Europe, not only bees but also other pollinators such as butterflies are a major focus, in addition to this the importance of hoverflies is undeniable (Topping et al., 2024). Butterflies have been threatened by factors such as agricultural intensification, climate change and habitat loss (Mills et al., 2017; Habel et al. 2019), resulting in declining and threatened European butterfly populations (van Swaay et al. 2010). These negative factors affect not only butterflies, but all other pollinator communities and threaten many wild pollinator populations. However, other pollinators such as hoverflies also make important contributions to agricultural production (Radar et al. 2016), but more than one-third of European hoverfly species are threatened (Vujić et al. 2022). The issue of declining pollinators has not only an impact on the ecology, but it also has a critical impact on agriculture, the economy, and society (Jarpla et al., 2024). In recent years, the observed decline of pollinator species has led to a significant shift in approach to pollination restoration studies in Europe. This alarming decline in pollinator species has not only raised ecological, economic and social concerns but has also led to increased research and EU projects into pollination restoration across Europe in the last years (European Commission, 2019; European Court of Auditors, 2020, European Commission, n.d)

In general, the definition of pollination service is the transfer of pollen grains to fertilize flowers, and we can consider it in two categories: one is on-farm benefits, necessary for seed set and fruit production in flowering plants and crops, and the other is off-farm benefits, necessary for crossing in non-cultivated flowering plants. In other words, pollination service is the term used to describe the mechanism by which pollinators, especially bees (wild and managed bees), insects, and other animals such as birds, transfer pollen from the male part of a flower to the female part of a flower, enabling the plant to produce fruit or seeds (Garbach et al., 2014).

As mentioned above, pollination services, are vital for both agricultural productivity and biodiversity, as they are responsible for the production of more than the 75% of crops (Klein et al., 2007), 35% of crop value, and 90% of all plants on Earth (Bennett et al., 2020), contributing an estimated US\$127 to US\$152 billion to global economic welfare (Peixoto et al., 2022). Despite their importance, pollinator populations are declining in Europe due to several motives and phenomena (Porto et al., 2020; Dicks et al., 2021). Current agricultural practices, characterized by pesticide use, habitat degradation, and monoculture, contribute to pollinator losses, especially in bee populations, and pose ecological, economic, and social risks (Goulson et al., 2015; Potts et al., 2010). While pollinator, pollination restoration, and conservation efforts have become more important, especially in the last two decades (Van der Sluijs & Goulson, 2016; IPBES, 2019), there is a gap in research to provide a better understanding of pollinator losses and pollination restoration especially at the transdisciplinary interface (Polk, 2014; Baumgärtner et al., 2008).

The importance of transdisciplinary studies in research with economic, ecological, and socio-institutional dimensions, such as pollination restoration, is undeniably significant (Polk, 2014; Exeler et al., 2009). However, most of the existing methodological approaches in the literature, such as laboratory or model-based studies, cannot adequately express the real-life dynamics of this issue (Prendergast & Ollerton, 2021). Ecological-economic modelling, which is used to analyse and manage the interactions between economics and ecosystems, is not enough to bridge this gap, even though it comes close to establishing the sociological and economic link. In this context, the Living Lab (LL) approach, which is based on real-life conditions and the interdisciplinary integration approach, is one of the most ideal co-innovation methodological approaches to fill this scientific gap (Westerman, 2014; Knickel, 2023).

LLs are defined as an approach to a knowledge-creation, co-innovation, and social learning ecosystem in which a scientific methodology of a transdisciplinary nature is deployed to develop and test socio-economic applications in real-life environments (Westerman, 2014; Knickel, 2023). The EU also defines Living Labs as “user-centered, open innovation ecosystems based on a systematic user co-creation approach that integrates research and innovation processes into real-life communities and environments”. Living Labs broadly have a twofold function: to enable the direct involvement of actors (e.g. farmers) in setting environmental goals through participatory methodologies (normative legitimization) and to assist policy implementation through collective action that demonstrates its advantages to both actors and society as a whole (cognitive legitimization). The common idea of Living Labs is to create partnerships between different parts of society, e.g. public organizations, private companies,

academia, people and the environment, to create an environment where they can work together, innovate and discuss together (Carayannis et al., 2012). Furthermore, Living Labs assume that bringing together a wider range of participants with different backgrounds, lifestyles, ages, genders, expertise and experiences will create and foster more useful, sustainable new ideas (Lupp et al., 2021), and the Living Lab approach is often described as ‘user-centered’, meaning that the people who use or benefit from a solution or innovation, i.e. stakeholders, are continuously involved throughout the process (Knickel et al., 2023; Lupp et al., 2021).

In this perspective, LLs which focus on pollination restoration play a crucial role in bridging the existing transdisciplinary gap (Basaran et al., 2024). Furthermore, the integration of the co-innovation process within the participatory approach applied in LLs with an ecological-economic modelling framework ensures the development of a more robust and comprehensive methodology to create knowledge and innovation (Aniche et al., 2024).

Moreover, it is not only the establishment of LLs that is crucial but also the necessity of comprehensive monitoring frameworks to ensure the effectiveness and success of these dynamic structures (Ramos et al., 2004) the progress of LLs over the years, and the change in ecological and social perspectives in the case study area (Knickel, 2023).

The monitoring framework may depend on the purpose, approach, and principles of the LL. Therefore, it is crucial to have an accurate theoretical framework to monitor and evolve the LL. Hence, if the background of a research framework is not sufficient, a theoretical framework is needed that combines multiple scientific studies and builds on a more concrete scientific background to monitor the LL.

In this context, this research aims to develop an integrated theoretical framework for monitoring the LL based on 3 different scientific frames, starting from existing Living Labs which focuses on pollination restoration across Europe. This framework is constructed on three pillars, namely the socio-ecological systems framework approach, the principles of innovation economy, and the participatory social learning approach, is shaped by the integration of 4 methodological academic studies: Ostrom's Social-Ecological Systems framework (SEs), Evenson's AKAP Sequential Model and Vecchio et al.'s AKAIE Model, and inspired by Knickel et al.'s study about collaborative learning in transdisciplinary LLs (Ostrom, 2009; Evenson, 1997; Vecchio et al., 2023; Knickel et al., 2023).

First, the main pillar of this study is Elinor Ostrom's Social-Ecological Systems framework (SEs)(Ostrom, 2009). SEs, illustrated in Figure 1, provide a solid theoretical foundation

that offers a comprehensive approach to understanding the complex interrelationships between social and ecological components of 'society and nature'. With this framework, Ostrom emphasizes governance structures, collective cooperation between different stakeholders, and the importance of local communities in managing the sharing of resources. Key components of the SESs framework are collective action, polycentric management, and multidisciplinary approaches. The framework was developed by Ostrom (2009) using a multi-level approach, which was later updated by McGinnis & Ostrom (2014) to increase its depth and comprehensiveness. The first level of the framework defines the subsystems of an SESs, which are divided into resource system, resource units, governance systems and actors (Ostrom, 2009; McGinnis & Ostrom, 2014). The second-level variables of the framework provide a deeper and more detailed understanding under each subsystem, and thus the framework allows for the development of third-level variables that further contextualize the analysis (McGinnis and Ostrom, 2014). This version of the SESs Framework, co-developed by Ostrom and McGinnis, makes SESs a method that can be easily applied in a wide range of fields. In addition, it allows the SESs framework to be more easily adapted and improved for different topics (Guimarães et al., 2018). As mentioned, the SESs framework is a method that can be used in a wide range of fields, so it is argued that the framework needs further adaptation and refinement for further topics which are specified. Thus, although SESs have a multi-disciplinary perspective on collaboration between different stakeholders, and provide governance mechanisms, however still SESs do not completely cover the core issues that we seek to monitor in our pollinator restoration LLs, such as the economics of innovation and participatory social learning, and therefore need to be combined with other methodologies. At the same time, the data obtained from the indicators developed within the framework of SESs are also created for use in the ecological model to be run. And this demonstrates once again why SESs are the cornerstone of this theoretical framework.

Figure 1. SES Framework (Ostrom 2009)

Secondly, an innovation economics approach was needed to systematically explore innovation processes. In this context, one of the strongest theoretical cornerstones of this theoretical framework was the Awareness Knowledge Adoption Product (AKAP) Sequence model (Evenson, 1997). However, the Product stage in this model did not fully match the objective of the study, and an extension version of AKAP, the Awareness Knowledge Adoption Implementation Effectiveness (AKAIE) model (Vecchio et al., 2023), was later adopted. As an extension of the AKAP model, it addresses the different stages of knowledge innovation and innovative change in a way that is more in line with the objective of LLs. These models emphasize the progression from awareness to activity during the adoption and application of knowledge in the innovation process. In other words, these are models for understanding both the different levels of adoption and the impact of the innovation created in terms of the environmental, economic, and social benefits generated. So, it fits perfectly with our research objective in our pollination restoration LLs. In other words, AKAP and its extended version AKAIE provide a theoretical background that is perfectly suited to our study as it provides important insights into the scalability and dissemination of the innovations and processes developed in LLs.

The third pillar of this theoretical framework is the participatory social learning approach, which emphasizes stakeholder participation and co-creation of knowledge innovation in a transdisciplinary environment due to the LLs' nature. In this context, although it could be developed within the other two theoretical studies, it could not provide a framework of sufficient depth in line with the objective of the research. And the participatory social learning approach was inspired by the article by Knickel et al., (2023) that examines how collaboration occurs and the role of social learning in transdisciplinary research. Analysing

the dynamics of participatory and social learning in LL, inspired by this article, has allowed us to develop indicators that allow us to monitor more deeply how social learning is shaped by knowledge, action, and relationships, bringing our theoretical framework of monitoring to the desired scope in line with the objectivity of the study. In addition, through this paper, encouraging stakeholders to share local experiences, knowledge, and innovation while monitoring normative and cognitive learning processes and diffusion of innovations has been strongly integrated into the theoretical framework of monitoring.

The framework developed in this study provides an integrated theoretical framework for monitoring indicators for LLs to monitor sustainable pollination restoration co-creation innovations in living labs. This framework enhances the LLs which will be combined with an ecological-economical modelling approach that aims to analyse these multi-dimensional, transdisciplinary dynamics focusing on pollination restoration at the science-society-policy interface. This framework is adaptable to different concepts. Indeed, supports policy-making and effective knowledge co-creation in LLs.

The key research question of this study is: How can an integrated theoretical monitoring framework be developed to investigate and develop the promotion and sustainability of pollinator restoration strategies among European farmers in the light of economic, socio-institutional, and ecological determinants?

The overall structure of the study takes the form of 4 chapters, including this context chapter which is the first chapter. The second chapter is concerned with the objective used for this study. The third chapter lays out the theoretical dimensions and methodology of the research. Finally, the results and conclusions chapter provides the results of this study and a brief summary and critique of the findings.

Objective

The main purpose of this study is to develop an integrated theoretical framework of monitoring measurement to examine how pollinator restoration strategies can be promoted and sustained among European farmers in light of economic, socio-institutional, and ecological determinants. In particular, a theoretical framework with 3 pillars: the socio-ecological system framework approach, the principle of innovation economics, and the participatory social learning approach, is developed for monitoring indicators that illustrate the role of LLs in co-developing innovative pollination restoration practices for stakeholders at the science-society-policy interface. This theoretical framework is also designed to provide indicators for fundamental data that will enable the extraction of economic and ecological variables required for an ecological-economic modelling methodology developed in harmony with the LLs.

Therefore, this research aims to develop a multidimensional monitoring indicator theoretical framework with a strong theoretical background to transdisciplinary assess pollination restoration's socio-ecological measurements, knowledge innovation, co-creation, and processes implemented in LL.

Methodology

The overall methodological framework of this study takes a multi-dimensional approach to monitoring pollinator restoration LLs as transdisciplinary, co-innovation and social learning environments in pan-Europe within the Horizon Europe RestPoll project, while developing an integrated core monitoring theoretical framework with a multi-method approach. Europe is a continent rich in biodiversity and wild pollinators and therefore matters such as animal pollination and pollination restoration are of particular interest; the main focus of this research is explored through 16 LLs spread across 14 European countries, which constitute the main case areas of this study. These 14 countries are: France, Germany, Ireland, Greece, Italy, Denmark, the United Kingdom, the Netherlands, Spain, Latvia, Switzerland, Hungary, and Ukraine.

Figure 2. Map of the Living Labs

One project of the European Union that emerged from these approaches is RestPoll, funded by Horizon Europe, a transdisciplinary research-innovation project using a LL methodology that aims to provide society with the tools to reverse the decline of wild pollinators. Another fundamental goal of Restpoll is to position Europe as a global leader in pollinator restoration.

The aim of these 16 RestPoll LLs, representing a variety of agricultural farm types and geographical regions across Europe, is to bridge the gap between research and

by combining the conceptual themes of these 4 key articles based on the integration of interdisciplinary approaches. Thus, both bio-physical/ecological 'sub-indicators' and socio-economic 'knowledge flow indicators' were identified under 2 main headings for the three primary phases of LLs are delineated as follows: the first phase, 'Exploration', involves the identification of the current state and the design of potential future states; the second phase, 'Experimentation', pertains to the empirical testing of one or more proposed future states in real-life contexts; and the third phase, 'Evaluation', consists of assessing the impact of the experiment on the current state, thereby facilitating the iterative development of the future state (Evans et al., 2017). Biophysical/ecological sub-indicators are parameters that provide an assessment of the measurable biological and physical characteristics of an ecosystem to provide insight into the health and functioning quality of the ecosystem. These sub-indicators are crucial for understanding and monitoring the impact of ecological disturbances, changes, and restoration on the ecosystem. In this context, the bio-physical/ecological sub-indicators represent the biological and physical parameters used in this study to monitor pollination restoration. The socio-economic 'knowledge flow indicators' are indicators that assess the transfer and impact of knowledge within and between different socio-economic systems, expressing the phenomena that influence issues such as innovation and economic development. These indicators are important for understanding how knowledge is created (internally and externally), shared, and utilized. It provides an understanding of how information has economic and social consequences (Kriegler et al., 2012) In this study, the socio-economic "knowledge flow indicators" were used to monitor and inform social learning, and knowledge flow on pollination restoration in LLs. In addition to that, the validation of the monitoring indicators developed within this theoretical framework is not only an internal procedure, but also an external one carried out through a multidisciplinary group of experts from pan-Europe. Throughout the process, the indicators have been developed in the context of meetings and procedures with these experts.

The indicators created under these two main headings have been transformed into the type of question format, following certain ethical and scientific guidelines, and are monitored through a questionnaire administered at the annual LL meetings. This questionnaire was prepared by converting the indicators into questions. The distribution of these questionnaires to stakeholders is subject to a systematic monitoring and evaluation process throughout the survey LL process. These surveys are conducted in each LL through a self-administered questionnaire method in digital (e.g. Google Forms) or paper format. In the data collection process, there is no obligation on the method of distribution of the questionnaires to stakeholders; each LL can choose to conduct online

or face-to-face surveys, depending on the characteristics and wishes of its stakeholder structure.

However, in order to achieve a standardized data structure to be used in the modelling approach, it was mandatory to save all questionnaire results in the final Excel format. This facilitates comparability and holistic analysis of data collected at different LLs. Each LL should act appropriately, systematically, and ethically when collecting data, ensuring that the collection, organization, and exporting of data to Excel complies with standards and ethics.

In sum, the theoretical framework of monitoring indicators developed in this study forms the basis of this methodology and will be supported by detailed information in the results section, providing a more robust perspective.

Results and Conclusions

As a result, as seen from this entire article, the creation of a comprehensive monitoring theoretical framework focusing on socio-ecological topics is not easy (Kriegler et al., 2012), and the creation of this theoretical framework, which is highly transdisciplinary in structure, has been a long and labour-intensive process. After long studies on what LLs need to be monitored, which methodology will better analyse LLs without neglecting any crucial points, and how to monitor this complex structure in the most adequate framework, the cornerstones of the theoretical framework for monitoring were selected and blended in harmony with each other. Then, the monitoring indicators creation process started according to this theoretical framework for monitoring.

A priority in the development of these monitoring indicators has been to establish robust indicators for the social dimensions. The second of the monitoring indicators workshops with experts mentioned earlier was held in Freiburg at the end of 2024 and included a focus group workshop with experts to discuss the indicators. During the workshop, ecological data and indicators related to ecological-economic modelling were also discussed, and ecological experts were commissioned to further develop indicators in this area. However, at the end of the process, it was decided that the indicators related to dimensions such as “Socio-economic Impacts,” “Ecological Outcomes,” “Resource Units” and “Resource System” would be monitored under the authority and responsibility of the work packages (WPs) responsible for the CSAs (Case Study Areas) within the scope of the project, with the aforementioned expert ecologists working in these WPs. Therefore, these dimensions are not included in this set of indicators specific to Living Labs. Thanks to this distribution of tasks, coordination and coherence between the project and Living Labs were strengthened, and unnecessary workload was prevented.

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

However, all the remaining indicators are presented in the table below in their finalized form after a multi-stage evaluation process. Following two Steering Group meetings with experts and LL leaders, the practical applicability of the theoretically developed monitoring indicators was tested through the LLs monitoring indicator questionnaire and through evaluations with stakeholders and LL responsible person after the annual Living Labs meeting at RestPoll Living Lab in Somerset, UK. Thus, the questionnaire and indicators prepared under this theoretical framework have been tested, and the feedback received afterwards has made it the most suitable for reality. And finally, after the 3rd steering group meeting, the indicators and questionnaire were validated by the LLs' responsible persons and experts and shared with all LLs in the project.

Dimension	Indicator	TO WHOM	
Stakeholder Characteristics and Engagement	0) Participation level	LL Leader	
	0.1) Total number of participants		
	0.2) Total number of participants by gender, age, and education Level		
	0.3 Types of actors		
	0.4) Participant involvement		
	0.5) Governance level		
	0.6) Degree of Management LL		
	0.7) Institutional Support and Contributions		
	0.8) Knowledge exchange		
Social Interactions and Engagement	1) Role in decision-making	LL Stakeholders	
	2) Stakeholder familiarity		
	3) Networking with LL stakeholders		
	Governance and Institutional Capacity		4) LL impact on Local Policies
			Processes and Adaptation
	6) Self-development		
	Interactions and Ecological Systemic Changes		7) Effectiveness of stakeholder co-design in pollination restoration
			8) Knowledge about reducing ecosystem Impacts
			9) Agricultural ecosystem impacts
	Awareness on Pollination		10) Awareness on innovations in pollination
Knowledge on Pollination Restoration	11) Knowledge on the importance of pollination and its impact on ecology before the project	LL Stakeholders	
	12) Knowledge of restoration measures		
Adoption on Pollination Restoration	13) Keen to adopt knowledge		
	14) Trust and collaboration		

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

Atmosphere and Social Environment of the Living Lab	15) Social Climate and Atmosphere	
	16) Participant Comfort in Contributing	
Socio-economic Impacts	(Not included, monitoring in CSA WPs)	Relevant WPs
Ecological outcomes	(Not included, monitoring in CSA WPs)	
Resource Units	(Not included, monitoring in CSA WPs)	
Resource System	(Not included, monitoring in CSA WPs)	

The final monitoring indicators, built on the theoretical framework, successfully provide systematic, comprehensive monitoring and evaluation of essential processes in LLs, focusing on pollination restoration, which is required in the literature. At the same time, the theoretical framework enables us to assess stakeholder co-design, innovation processes, and ecological-economic outcomes through quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis, supporting the formulation of adaptive policy recommendations and effective sustainable management strategies. This monitoring indicators tool is prepared as a questionnaire by translating monitoring indicators into questions. The questionnaire is answered by stakeholders and LLs leaders separately in each living lab, either online or face-to-face, at the annual LL meetings organized each year for systemic monitoring, or afterwards.

The sequence that was developed by combining the AKAP and AKAIE sequence models was used as a classification framework for monitoring indicators within the monitoring framework and provided a valuable conceptual perspective in the indicator development process. Each indicator is associated with innovation stages: Awareness, Knowledge, Adoption, and Impact. For example, the indicators of degree of management LL, the stakeholder familiarity, agricultural ecosystem impacts, awareness on innovations in pollination restoration, and knowledge on the importance of pollination and its impact on ecology before the project was developed to capture the 'Awareness' stage. The knowledge exchange, effectiveness of stakeholder co-design in pollination restoration, knowledge about Reducing Ecosystem Impacts, and knowledge on restoration measures indicators address the 'Knowledge' stage. The 'Adoption' stage is reflected through the institutional support and contributions, role in decision-making, , feedback, effectiveness of stakeholder co-design in pollination restoration, knowledge about reducing ecosystem Impacts, keen to adopt, social climate and atmosphere, trust, and collaboration indicators. Finally, indicators such as participant involvement, self-development, degree of management level, networking with LL stakeholders, and LL impact on local policies

are aligned with the Impact stage. This categorization helped to relate the theoretical innovation dynamics to measurable dimensions in Living Lab practices.

Additionally, it should also be noted that this monitoring framework is flexible and adaptable for use in a wide variety of ecological, social, and geographical environments. The main structure of this monitoring framework allows for the selection or modification of specific indicators and data collection methods, such as those related to different ecological issues, different geographical, socio-cultural conditions, local ecological conditions, community needs, and available resources, in a manner appropriate to the specific context. For instance, this study is a framework developed to monitor living labs in European countries, but it is possible to adapt this monitoring framework to other geographical areas and ecological issues by adjusting the indicators appropriately to the situation and subject matter in other geographical areas, and perhaps making minor changes to the indicators as needed. This framework was also created with the intention of serving as a guide for other studies. Thus, this monitoring framework, developed specifically for this approach, enables its application across different geographical areas, ecological issues, and social systems, maintaining harmony between them.

In conclusion, this study aimed to design a multidimensional monitoring theoretical framework in line with a gap in the literature and to evaluate 16 pollination restoration LLs in Europe, aligned with established ecological-economic modelling, with monitoring indicators based on this theoretical framework. Synthesizing three main theoretical perspectives, Ostrom's social-ecological systems approach (2009), the principle of innovation economics through AKAP sequence and AKAIE sequence models (Evenson, 1997; Vecchio et al., 2023), and a participatory social learning approach (Knickel et al., 2023), a robust multidisciplinary set of monitoring indicators covering stakeholder interactions, innovation processes, and ecological-economic outcomes has been developed to fill a gap in the literature. The findings of the study demonstrate that LLs can be monitored from a broad scientific perspective, providing a comprehensive theoretical framework for monitoring stakeholder interactions, innovation processes, and ecological-economic outcomes in LL. The co-creation process of stakeholder engagement, knowledge, and innovation, conceptualized in a transdisciplinary setting, enables the monitoring of the implementation of sustainable restoration strategies in agricultural systems through a robust theoretical framework. While the results are in line with studies in the literature (e.g., Ostrom, 2009; Evenson, 1997; Vecchio et al., 2023; Knickel et al., 2023), these studies are not sufficient individually in many different respects, and together they offer a new comprehensive approach to monitoring the co-interaction of socio-ecological, learning and innovation dynamics.

The lack of such a comprehensive and multidimensional theoretical framework for monitoring LLs in the existing literature is addressed in this study by integrating Ostrom's (2009) social-ecological systems approach, the innovation economy perspective via using the AKAP sequence model by

Evenson (1997) and the AKAIE Sequence by Vecchio et al. (2023), and a participatory social learning approach inspired and strengthened by Knickel's (2023) article, thus filling the scientific gap in the literature. In particular, this study fills an important gap in the literature by demonstrating the need for a multidisciplinary, comprehensive, long-term multidimensional way monitoring framework for comparisons between LLs, both within LLs themselves over the years and between LLs within their network.

However, the study has some limitations. So, since this study focuses on LLs in Europe in a specific project, there are limitations such as regional and project differences in the framework developed. For future scientific studies is recommended to go further with this study. Such as, testing the applicability of this methodology in practice, to go beyond this theoretical framework to test its applicability to LLs focusing on other socio-ecological issues over more than 2 years, and finally focusing on a broader and more detailed examination of the indicators developed within this monitoring theoretical framework in another paper.

In conclusion, although our study has some limitations, it offers a monitoring theoretical framework that can be adapted to innovative platforms such as LLs in transdisciplinary settings, especially those focusing on socio-ecological issues, and provides important contributions to monitor the process of policymaking, social learning and the development of efficient governance practices.

Acknowledgement

The development and improvement of this monitoring framework would not have been possible without the valuable guidance and dedicated support provided by the RestPoll project's LLs monitoring steering group during the development of the monitoring framework (special thanks to Amibeth Thompson, Anda Ādamsons-Fiskoviča, David Kleijn, George Vlontzos, Lynn Dicks, Mariia Fedoriak, Martin Hvarregaard Thorsøe, Nicola Gallai, Per Angelstam, Sara Leonhardt, and Tom Breeze), along with the active contributions and feedback from LL leaders and responsible persons of the RestPoll LLs who participated in workshops, online meetings and provided practical insights. Their involvement has been invaluable in the scope of the research, its methodology, the

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures:

Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

development of its implementation, and the adaptation of indicators to real-life conditions. We appreciate all participants for their collective contributions, willingness to share their expertise and collaborations, their feedback, and for helping to ensure the framework's accuracy and depth, as well as for sharing their valuable time with us. Additionally, we would like to extend our special thanks to Michael Garratt, leader of Apple Orchards in Kent LL, which was chosen as the pilot Living Lab from among 16 RestPoll Living Labs. His valuable feedback, reviews, and guidance were essential in developing and refining the indicators for real-life conditions. We are also grateful to Alexandra-Maria Klein, the RestPoll project coordinator, for her continuous support.

References

1. Aniche, L. Q., Edelenbos, J., Gianoli, A., Enseñado, E. M., Makousiari, E., DeLosRíos-White, M. I., Caruso, R., & Zalokar, S. (2024). Boosting co-creation of Nature-based Solutions within Living Labs: Interrelating enablers using Interpretive Structural Modelling. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 161, 103873. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2024.103873>
2. Baumgärtner, S., Becker, C. U., Frank, K., Müller, B., & Quaas, M. F. (2008). Relating the philosophy and practice of ecological economics: the role of concepts, models, and case studies in inter- and transdisciplinary sustainability research. *Ecological Economics*, 67(3), 384–393. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ECOLECON.2008.07.018>
3. Biesmeijer, J. C., Roberts, S. P. M., Reemer, M., Ohlemüller, R., Edwards, M., Peeters, T., Schaffers, A. P., Potts, S. G., Kleukers, R., Thomas, C. D., Settele, J., & Kunin, W. E. (2006). Parallel declines in pollinators and insect-pollinated plants in Britain and the
4. Bottero, I., Dominik, C., Schweiger, O., Albrecht, M., Attridge, E., Brown, M. J., ... & Stout, J. C. (2023). Impact of landscape configuration and composition on pollinator communities across different European biogeographic regions. *Frontiers in ecology and evolution*, 11, 1128228.
- Arbetman, M. P., Gleiser, G., Morales, C. L., Williams, P., & Aizen, M. A. (2017). Global decline of bumblebees is phylogenetically structured and inversely related to species range size and pathogen incidence. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 284(1859). <https://doi.org/10.1098/RSPB.2017.0204>
5. Cameron, S. A., Lozier, J. D., Strange, J. P., Koch, J. B., Cordes, N., Solter, L. F., & Griswold, T. L. (2011). Patterns of widespread decline in North American bumble bees. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 108(2), 662–667. <https://doi.org/10.1073/PNAS.1014743108/-/DCSUPPLEMENTAL/ST06.DOC>
6. European Commission. (n.d.). RestPoll: Restoring Pollinator Habitats across European Agricultural Landscapes based on Multi-Actor Participatory Approaches. <https://ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures/restpoll>
7. European Commission. (n.d.). RestPoll: Restoring Pollinator Habitats across European Agricultural Landscapes based on Multi-Actor Participatory Approaches. <https://ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures/restpoll>
8. European Court of Auditors. (2020). Protection of wild pollinators in the EU – Commission initiatives have not borne fruit (Special Report No. 15/2020). Publications Office of the European Union. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/386c9925-860d-11eb-af5d-01aa75ed71a1>
9. Exeler, N., Kratochwil, A., & Hochkirch, A. (2009). Restoration of riverine inland sand dune complexes: implications for the conservation of wild bees. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 46(5), 1097–1105. <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1365-2664.2009.01701.X>
10. Evenson R. (1997); The economic contributions of agricultural extension to agricultural and rural development, in Swanson B.E., Bentz R.P., Sofranko A. (eds.): Improving agricultural extension. A reference manual, Rome, FAO.
11. Fornoff, Felix et al. (2024). RestPoll case-study network. Deliverable D1.1 EU Horizon RestPoll Project, Grant agreement No. 101082102.
12. Goulson, D., Lye, G. C., & Darvill, B. (2008). Decline and conservation of wild bumble bees. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 53(Volume 53, 2008), 191–208. <https://doi.org/10.1146/ANNUREV.ENTO.53.103106.093454/CITE/REFWORKS>
13. Hart, S. L. (1995). A natural-resource-based view of the firm. *Academy of management review*, 20(4), 986–1014.
14. Keyson, D., Guerra-Santin, O., & Lockton, D. (2017). Living labs. Design and Assessment of Sustainable Living. Netherlands: Springer.
15. Knickel, M., Caniglia, G., Knickel, K., Šūmane, S., Maye, D., Arcuri, S., ... & Brunori, G. (2023). Lost in a haze or playing to partners' strengths? Learning to collaborate in three transdisciplinary European Living Labs. *Futures*, 152, 103219.
16. Lanssens, B., François, L., Hambuckers, A., Moen, M., Anders, T., Tölle, M., ... & Remy, L. (2022,

- May). Assessing the effects of climate and land use changes on the distribution and growth of important plants species for pollinators. In EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts (pp. EGU22-4559). Netherlands. Science, 313(5785), 351–354. https://doi.org/10.1126/SCIENCE.1127863/SUPPL_FILE/BIESMEIJER.SOM.PDF
17. Nieto, A., Roberts, S. P. M., Kemp, J., Rasmont, P., Kuhlmann, M., García Criado, M., Biesmeijer, J. C., Bogusch, P., Dathe, H. H., de la Rúa, P., de Meulemeester, T., Dehon, M., Dewulf, A., Ortiz-Sánchez, F. J., Lhomme, P., Pauly, A., Potts, S. G., Praz, C., Q., Window, J., & Michez, D. (2014). European Red List of Bees. IUCN Global Species Programm. <https://doi.org/10.2779/77003>
 18. Ostrom, E. (2009) A General Framework for Analysing Sustainability of Social-Ecological Systems. Science, 325, 419-422. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1172133>
 19. Persson, A. S., Hederström, V., Ljungkvist, I., Nilsson, L., & Kendall, L. (2023). Citizen science initiatives increase pollinator activity in private gardens and green spaces. *Frontiers in Sustainable Cities*, 4, 1099100.
 20. Polk, M. (2014). Achieving the promise of Transdisciplinarity: a critical exploration of the relationship between transdisciplinary research and societal problem solving. *Sustainability Science*, 9(4), 439–451. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11625-014-0247-7>
 21. Potts, S. G., Biesmeijer, J. C., Kremen, C., Neumann, P., Schweiger, O., & Kunin, W. E. (2010). Global pollinator declines: Trends, impacts and drivers. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, 25(6), 345–353. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2010.01.007>
 22. Prendergast, K. S., & Ollerton, J. (2021). Plant-pollinator networks in Australian urban bushland remnants are not structurally equivalent to those in residential gardens. *Urban Ecosystems*, 24(5), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11252-020-01089-W> Programme under project No. 101082102.
 23. Ramos, T. B., Caeiro, S., & de Melo, J. J. (2004). Environmental indicator frameworks to design and assess environmental monitoring programs. *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal*, 22(1), 47–62. <https://doi.org/10.3152/147154604781766111> This project receives funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Framework
 24. Van Dooren, T. J. M. (2019). Assessing species richness trends: Declines of bees and bumblebees in the Netherlands since 1945. *Ecology and Evolution*, 9(23), 13056–13068. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ECE3.5717>
 25. Van Swaay, C., Cuttelod, A., Collins, S., Maes, D., Munguira, M. L., Šašić, M., Settele, J., Verovnik, R., Verstrael, T., Warren, M., Wiemers, M., & Wynhoff, I. (2010). European Red List of Butterflies. Publications Office of the European Union.
 26. Vecchio, Y., Masi, M., & Adinolfi, F. (2023). From the AKAP to AKAIE model to assess the uptake of technological innovations in the aquaculture sector. *Reviews in Aquaculture*, 15(2), 772-784.
 27. Vujić, A., Gilbert, F., Flinn, G., Englefield, E., Varga, Z., Ferreira, C. C., Eggert, F., Woolcock, S., Böhm, M., Vbra, J., Mergy, R., Ssymank, A., van Steenis, W., Aracil, A., Földesi, R., Grković, A., Mazanek, L., Nedeljković, Z., Pennards, G. W. A., ... Veličković, N. (n.d.). The European Red List of Hoverflies. www.iucn.org/species